

VIII International Congress on Architectural Envelopes BRESAER. Breakthrough Solutions for Adaptable Envelopes in Building Refurbishment

Imanol Aguirre¹, Asier Azpiazu¹, Isabel Lacave², Izaskun Álvarez³, Roberto Garay³

¹Department of Innovation, LKS, e-mail: iagirre@lksgroup.com

²Technology & Innovation Division, Acciona Infraestructuras

³Sustainable Construction Division, Tecnalia

Key words: Envelope, Refurbishment, Adaptable, Renewable, Control

Abstract

This paper presents an innovative and standardized system for roofs and façades, integrating different technological solutions that improve the energetic efficiency, thermal, acoustic and light comfort, as well as air quality in buildings. The BRESAER system combines industrialized active and passive solutions and nanotechnology over one common modular, versatile and light substructure.

The system consists of a base of industrialized and adaptable substructure to which different coverings are installed: Modular ventilated façade with nanotechnology application, multilayer panels of thermal insulation and fiber reinforced concrete with nanotechnology properties, metallic active envelopes connected to the ventilation system and windows with automated dynamic slats with high thermic properties for light and solar radiation control. The system of multi-response envelope is adaptable to the climate and orientation of the building, which allows the replicability of the system on actual inefficient buildings.

The overall challenge and required policies at EU level are presented, along with the specific objectives and strategies of BRESAER to solve these issues. Then the characteristics of the whole system are explained, followed by the analysis of each of the innovative elements that integrate the system. Finally, conclusions learnt in the project and future ambitions are presented.

1 Introduction

In the present framework of the new construction stoppage, building sector is forced to adapt to new development paths and to adopt strategies to face a period of changing requirements. Instead of building more, the current building stock is upgraded. The EU building stock contributes to 40% of

total energy consumption and 36% of CO₂ emissions [1]. The improvement of energy efficiency of this stock and the integration of renewable energies is, therefore, a priority.

Energy renovation allows to improve the energy efficiency, to adapt the spaces to the new comfort and standard requirements, as well as to extend the lifespan of the existing buildings. The adoption of energy saving measures is also a priority for European Commission [2], with the aim of: (i) reducing and optimizing the energy demand by the improvement of the thermal behaviour of the envelope and removing thermal bridges, (ii) incorporating renewable energy systems to get a net balance between the consumed and the produced energy (Nearly Zero Energy Buildings), (iii) using industrialized innovative elements for a fast and economic application of the system.

The transmission losses through the envelope of the building have a great influence in the energy consumption of the building. In temperate climates, building envelopes (façades and roofs) with “average” insulation values can contribute up to 27% of total energy consumption [3]. The envelope is, therefore, a key element to reduce building energy consumption, whose retrofitting can achieve more than 40% of total energy savings [4].

Nowadays, the envelope renovation is done exclusively in terms of energy efficiency by the addition of insulation. However, it has the potential to incorporate, additionally, active strategies to produce free energy, leading towards Nearly Zero Energy Buildings.

Every building has been traditionally considered as a unique product, which has limited prefabrication and modular system application. Retrofitting has not been considered as the scope of prefabrication market. At research level, some projects have been developed in this vein [5, 6], but they have not reached the market. The development of adaptable industrialized systems would enable the improvement of the quality of works and the reduction of execution times, reducing the inconveniences caused to the neighbours.

The innovation project BRESAER is being developed within this context, funded by the Horizon 2020 program (topic EeB-02-2014: “Adaptable envelopes integrated in building refurbishment projects”) with the objective of developing an innovative, cost-effective, adaptable and industrialized envelope system (façades and roofs) for buildings refurbishment. The BRESAER system is composed by passive and active technologies improving energy efficiency, thermal, acoustic and lighting comfort, and indoor air quality (IAQ). The whole building will be governed by an innovative Building Energy Management System covering a specific control system for governing several envelope functions and the energy facilities of the building, including the energy generated by the BRESAER system (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1: BRESAER system's scheme.

feasible investment return. The combination of the innovative and existing conventional solutions that allow to control the cost of installation while is adaptable to new indoor requirements and external climatic conditions, is the key issue of the BRESAER system.

Finally, the parameters required by BREEAM and LEED certifications have been analysed. These are sustainability assessment methods, applied in Master Plans, infrastructures and buildings, differentiated by the type of intervention: existing buildings, new construction or renovation. Aspects related to energy efficiency, recyclability of materials and waste generation, among others, have been considered in the design of the system. Each façade solution has been analysed separately, but also as a whole. Moreover, Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Cost have been evaluated to know the profitability of the system from the economic perspective and the used resources from cradle to grave.

Furthermore, simulations have been performed to calculate the structural, thermal and acoustic performance of the envelope elements, additional systems and dynamic window. Three prototypes have been installed verifying the correct mechanical and energy performance (see Fig.3). Finally, the last laboratory tests have been developed, demonstrating the mechanical performance, fire resistance, wind resistance, impact, tightness and freezing of the BRESAER. The objective is to validate the system across Europe, in compliance with the requirements of the construction products directive.

Figure 3: Three finished prototypes.

3 Elements of Bresaer

3.1 Lightweight structural mesh

It consists of an industrialized extruded aluminium lightweight structural mesh installed over a continuous insulation layer, improving thermal-hydrimetric behaviour.

The main profiles have a cross section of 150 x 80 cm placed every 90 cm. Each covering system requires additional elements for the alignment and integration of all solutions. These elements are exchangeable and adaptable to allow the maintenance, variations and disassembly of the system. In addition, they can be quickly and easily installed.

The aluminium profiles are anchored in each band of existing slabs. These anchors ensure the verticality and horizontality of the façade, and are calculated specifically in each project, adapting to

the singularities of each existing building. The profile covers the distance of a floor, making easier the transport and especially the assembly of the aluminium profiles.

The connection of the profiles is done by hammerhead screws, which allow movement through the section groove of the profiles by a dry connection, adaptable and removable without damage or material loss.

The support structure of the Bresaer system is designed to integrate different envelope energy rehabilitation solutions, to guarantee their interchangeability and maintenance and to be structurally independent of the original façade. These factors have resulted in a new design of innovative, versatile and adaptable auxiliary structure.

In addition to these requirements, the economic viability should be ensured. Therefore, the profiles of the substructure should be standard profiles provided by extruded aluminum profiles suppliers.

On the other side, the requirement to allow the interchangeability of the different envelope solutions requests that the integrity of the structural section should be guaranteed in each permutation. This involves the exclusion of the self-drilling screws as a method to connect the profiles.

The profile typology that ensures all these conditions is the grooved tubular profile typology. The connections between this kind of profiles can be carried out in several different ways, all of them are detachable. In the specific case of the BRESAER substructure, the connections between profiles have been defined by brackets and "hammer head" screws inserted in the grooves.

Figure 4: Left: grooved tubular profile. Middle: "hammer head" screws. Right: profiles connection by brackets and "hammer head" screws. Source: Alu-stock (<http://www.alu-stock.es/>) (2018/02/08).

In order to achieve the integration of the different technologies in the same finishing exterior plane, different link elements have been defined between each technology and the substructure mesh. The connections between these elements and the substructure are defined according to the same philosophy as the connections among the grooved tubular profiles; they should be detachable to allow the solutions' interchangeability. The different envelope solutions are connected directly to these link elements.

Figure 5: Connection between different envelope solutions and the BRESAER substructure by different types of link elements.

Finally, the structural dimensioning of the BRESAER substructure (based on the requirements prescribed in the Eurocodes) has been carried out considering that the vertical profiles (main profiles of the substructure) are only fixed to the slabs of the building and consequently the installation of the BRESAER System is ensured in any building, regardless of the situation of preservation of the original façade.

3.2 Industrialized lightweight ventilated façade module

Ventilated façade modular system is an industrialized system developed by ULMA Architectural Solutions. It is a traditional finishing system of polymer concrete slabs fixed to a substructure, with an air chamber and a layer of insulation. The ventilated system is the traditional efficient system that best suits condensation problems and covering of thermal bridges.

The system needs specific cladding elements in order to align the different envelope systems. These cladding elements are installed on a horizontal grid of metal rail standardized by ULMA.

A photovoltaic glass that keeps the same modulation of the system has been developed throughout the project, producing electricity in a semi-transparent surface. The integration is done by an aluminium frame adaptable to the geometric components of the conventional system.

3.3 Multilayer Ultra High Performance Fibre Reinforced insulated panels

It has a high insulation potential covering large surfaces up to three meters high. It is composed by two layers: a high performance fibre-reinforced concrete external layer of three centimetres and a five centimetre polyurethane internal layer. The section in the cladding part is different in order to give higher structural capacity to the conformed panel.

The panel is complemented with a photovoltaic glass mechanically fixed to the external concrete layer, changing the façade to an active element.

The original design was refined after tests to enhance its mechanical performance with additional metallic ribs embedded in the panels. STAM, technology entity that works on the industrial innovation field, has developed the product.

3.4 Solar thermal active envelopes

Solarwall system is a perforated metal sheet façade connected to the Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) system. The design has been optimized in order to maximize the energy contribution through the heat accumulation in the air chamber, producing an air stream that travels to the inlet of the system's collectors.

The volume of the air chamber depends on the building and environment conditions. The Solarwall solution requires reviewing and adapting the design and the features of the technical solution in each implementation to achieve an optimal energetic performance.

The system is composed by elements of traditional industrialized lightweight ventilated façades, having a cheap solution with high-energy contribution.

3.5 Dynamic window with automatically controlled solar blinds

Dynamic windows are an integrated module in the BRESAER system, which control the sun radiation, lighting contribution and insulation by intelligent louvres. The blind has an aluminium perimeter frame, and can rotate the louvres to better adapt to internal needs.

The louvres of the blinds are made by sandwich panels with external layer of aluminium sheet and internal layer of high performance phenolic foam. This type of sandwich panel is not yet in the market. Therefore, it has been developed specifically for the blind production.

The window system has been developed by EURECAT, a Catalonian Research Centre.

3.6 Photocatalytic coatings on the external surfaces

The nanocoating is the last element of the system, which improves the energy efficiency. It is applied over the ULMA panels, STAM and EURECAT louvres. The role of a coating on the BRESAER is multifunctional: Apart from the aesthetic part combined with durability against weathering, the coating should reflect a great percentage of incident heat and at the same time exhibit photocatalytic, self-cleaning properties.

The coating or paint is composed by two layers. Firstly, a water repellent primer and, secondly, an exterior coating that protects from pollution, formation of mould and other harmful environmental effects.

This product has been developed by NANOPHOS, company that included nanotechnology in its coatings.

3.7 Building Energy Management System

BREASER is controlled by an ICT technology able to optimize the use of energy. The key is to transform the envelope not only in an active element, but also in a reactive element, which can balance the energy flows instantly.

The Building Energy Management System (BEMS) can measure and control both active elements of the envelope and building energy services. It is based on the combination of simulation-based control predictive methods for the optimization of the operation plans. BEMS controls and monitors buildings' HVAC systems, the active thermal envelope, the production and storage of the energy produced by the photovoltaic panels, and the dynamic window with automatic controlled blind, in order to maximize the energy efficiency of the building.

This product is being developed jointly by Cartif, Technological Research Centre in Valladolid and the Technological Centre of Acciona Construction.

4 Conclusions

The key issue of the BRESAER system is the possibility of applying industrialized solutions for energy efficient renovation by the combination of passive and active elements. Thus, in addition to improving the aesthetic of the building, the energy efficiency, the indoor air quality and thermal-hydrometric, acoustic and lighting performance, the system presents high versatility and lightness incorporating energy collecting systems and an efficient energy management.

Different envelope solutions can be added to the system by a metal mesh substructure anchored to the structure of the existing building. This substructure is scalable and adjustable to ensure a quick and systemic installation and allow the maintenance of the envelope elements.

The final design of the envelope system has been developed and refined through tests. The next step is to implement the system in a real demonstrator. The aim of the demonstrator is to validate all the mechanical, energetic, economic and comfort aspects the BRESAER system offers.

The demonstrator will be governed by an innovative Building Energy Management System, which controls the elements of the envelope and the energy consumption of the building, in order to quantify and compare the real energy savings with the previous simulations. These savings are added to the Life Cycle Assessment and the Payback calculation.

Reference

- [1] Directive 2010/31/UE of the European Parliament and the Council of 19th May related to building energy efficiency.
- [2] European Commission. *Energy Efficiency- Buildings. 2015*; Available in: <http://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/buildings>
- [3] Boonyatikarn, S., *Impact of Building Envelopes on Energy Consumption and Energy Design Guidelines*. Buildings II Conference - DOE Conference on the Thermal Performance of the Exterior Envelopes of Buildings; August 1982; Las Vegas: ASHRAE; 1983.
- [4] Aste N, Del Pero C; *Energy retrofit of commercial buildings: case study and applied methodology*. Energy Efficiency 2012(2):407-23.
- [5] Meefs Project, <http://www.meefs-retrofitting.eu/>
- [6] Kobler, R. et al., IEA ECBCS Annex 50 Report, *Retrofit Module Design Guide*, 2011